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Research Article

Molecular Docking And ADMET Predictions Of Substituted Cordyheptapeptide Derivatives: Evaluating Antifungal Potential Against The 5U32 Fungal RNA Kinase Complex

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ABSTRACT

Cyclic peptides, particularly cordyheptapeptide and its analogs derived from the Cordyceps fungal genus, have emerged as promising candidates for therapeutic applications due to their diverse biological activities, including antifungal properties. In this study, we conducted molecular docking analyses of substituted derivatives of cordyheptapeptide against the 5U32 fungal RNA kinase complex, a crucial target in fungal infections, using PyRx and Discovery Studio Visualizer. The objective was to assess the binding affinities of these derivatives and compare them with the standard antifungal drug, ketoconazole. All cordyheptapeptide derivatives adhered to Lipinski's rule, suggesting their potential for oral administration. The docking scores of the derivatives ranged from -7.9 to -9.7 kcal/mol, indicating strong binding affinity to the target protein. These results demonstrate the promising antifungal properties of the cordyheptapeptide derivatives, with several compounds exhibiting similar activities to ketoconazole. This study provides valuable insights into the potential of substituted cordyheptapeptide derivatives as novel antifungal agents, contributing to the development of alternative therapeutic strategies against fungal infections. Further research and optimization of these compounds may lead to the discovery of effective treatments for fungal diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Fungi, as ubiquitous micro-organisms, inhabit diverse environments and engage in symbiotic or endophytic relationships with a wide array of host organisms, utilizing various resources for their survival. Among these, marine fungal strains stand out for their ecological significance, owing to their

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capacity to produce a diverse range of specialized metabolites. These metabolites, which include alkaloids, polyketides, terpenoids, and peptides, play pivotal roles in ecological interactions and have garnered attention for their potential applications in various fields, particularly in medicine [1]. Peptide-based therapies have emerged as promising avenues for treating a multitude of diseases, including fungal infections. The unique characteristics of peptides, such as high affinity, specificity, and low toxicity, position them as advantageous alternatives to traditional chemical drugs. Among these peptides, cordyheptapeptide exemplifies beneficial properties that underscore the potential of peptides in therapeutic applications [2]. Bioactive peptides, defined as specific fragments of proteins whose activity stems from their amino acid composition and sequence, are abundant in both terrestrial and marine organisms. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in microorganism-derived peptides (MdPs) due to their distinctive molecular structures and a wide spectrum of associated bioactivities. These MdPs have demonstrated antimicrobial [3], antimalarial [4,5], antibacterial [6], cytotoxic [7,8], and antiviral activities [9], making them valuable targets for further exploration and development in biomedical research. In the peptide production process, the formation of the peptide bond is a crucial step, requiring the activation of carboxylic acid. This activation is typically achieved using peptide coupling reagents. If the activation of carboxylic acid is slow, these coupling reagents may degrade, rendering them ineffective in activating the carboxyl function. Common coupling reagents include carbodiimides, phosphonium and ammonium salts, fluoroformamidinium coupling reagents, organophosphorus reagents, and triazine coupling reagents [10]. In the investigation of the relationship between molecular size and cell permeability, researchers synthesized and studied

the properties of cordyheptapeptide A. Cordyheptapeptide A, originally found in *Cordyceps*, a fungus with pharmaceutical potential, belongs to a family of peptides that exhibit toxicity against bacteria, fungi, and various cancer cell lines. While its crystal structure and total synthesis have been reported, its biological targets and mechanism of action have remained unknown [11]. Fungal tRNA ligase (Trl1) is crucial for repairing RNA breaks with specific end structures, such as 2',3'-cyclic-PO₄, and 5'-OH ends, occurring during tRNA splicing and non-canonical mRNA splicing in the fungal unfolded protein response. Trl1 comprises C-terminal cyclic phosphodiesterase and central polynucleotide kinase domains, which work together to generate the necessary termini for sealing by an N-terminal ligase domain. Trl1 enzymes are present in all human fungal pathogens and are promising targets for antifungal drug discovery due to their unique domain compositions and mechanisms compared to mammalian RtcB-type tRNA splicing enzymes. Trl1 exhibits a distinctive preference for using GTP as a phosphate donor for the RNA kinase reaction [12]. In a recent study, the crystal structure of the kinase domain of Trl1 from *Candida albicans* has been elucidated, unveiling the presence of GDP and Mg²⁺ bound within the active site. This kinase domain showcases a P-loop phosphotransferase fold, characterized by a distinct 'G-loop' element that plays a pivotal role in conferring specificity towards guanine nucleotides. Notably, mutations observed in amino acids involved in interactions with the guanine nucleobase have been found to abrogate kinase activity in vitro and impede Trl1 function in vivo. These findings underscore the potential of Trl1 kinase as a viable target for antifungal interventions [13].

Fig.1: Cordyheptapeptide

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study of molecular docking was carried out on a system with computational specifications (HP Pavilion AMD Ryzen™ 5 Hexa Core 5500 APU @ 2.1GHz with turbo boost up to 4GHz Processor version 5500U and 16.00 GB RAM with 64-bit Windows-11 operating system).

- PubChem webservice
- Protein Data Bank
- BioviaDiscovery Studio visualizer
- PyRx, PubChem, Webservice
- Swiss dock

The Swiss ADME study methodology involves the following steps:

1. Input Compound Structure:

Input the chemical structure of the compound of interest using SMILES notation.

2. Calculation of Pharmacokinetics Parameters:

SwissADME calculates various pharmacokinetic parameters such as molecular weight, lipophilicity, water solubility, and permeability.

3. Prediction of Drug-Likeness:

Evaluate adherence to Lipinski's Rule of Five and other drug-likeness rules:

- a. Molecular weight < 500 g/mol
- b. LogP (miLogP) < 5
- c. Hydrogen bond donors < 5
- d. Hydrogen bond acceptors < 10
- e. Rule violations ≤ 2

4. Calculation of Physicochemical Properties:

Compute additional physicochemical properties such as polar surface area and number of rotatable bonds.

5. Visualization and Interpretation:

Present results in a user-friendly format for easy interpretation. The methodology of molecular docking involves several crucial steps to predict the binding orientation and affinity between a ligand and a receptor. Here's an overview of the main steps involved:

1. Preparation of Ligand and Receptor:

This step involves preparing the 3D structures of both the ligand (small molecule) and the receptor (typically a protein) for docking. This may include adding hydrogen atoms, assigning partial charges, and optimizing geometry.

2. Grid box generation:

A grid is generated around the receptor to define the search space for the ligand. This grid typically encompasses the active site or binding pocket of the receptor where ligand binding is expected to occur.

3. Scoring function selection:

Various scoring functions are available to evaluate the fitness of ligand binding within the receptor's binding site. These scoring functions estimate binding affinity based on factors such as electrostatic interactions, van der Waals forces, hydrogen bonding, and desolvation energies.

4. Docking algorithm selection:

Different algorithms are employed to explore the conformational space of the ligand and predict its optimal binding pose within the receptor's binding site. These algorithms include stochastic methods like genetic algorithms, simulated annealing, or deterministic methods like Lamarckian genetic algorithm (LGA) and Monte Carlo-based techniques.

5. Docking simulation:

The ligand is systematically positioned and oriented within the receptor's binding site using the chosen docking algorithm. The ligand's

conformational flexibility may be accounted for by allowing it to rotate, translate, and adapt its shape during the docking process.

6. Scoring and ranking:

After docking, the conformations generated are scored using the selected scoring function to assess the binding affinity of each ligand-receptor complex. Ligands are ranked based on their predicted binding energies or scores.

7. Analysis and visualization:

The docked complexes are analyzed to identify key interactions such as hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interactions, and π - π stacking between the ligand and receptor residues. Visualization tools like Biovia Discovery Studio or PyMOL are commonly used for this purpose. By following these steps, molecular docking enables the prediction and analysis of ligand-receptor interactions, facilitating drug discovery and structure-based drug design efforts.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The ADME study and its correlation with Lipinski's rule provides valuable insights into the drug-likeness and potential pharmacokinetic behavior of cordyheptapeptide compounds and their derivatives. Firstly, the ADME study is crucial for assessing the safety and efficacy of pharmaceutical substances by evaluating their absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion within an organism's body. Lipinski's rule, a widely accepted guideline in drug discovery, outlines specific molecular properties that are important for drug pharmacokinetics. These properties include molecular weight, hydrophobicity, hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, and the number of violations of Lipinski's rule. According to Lipinski's rule, for a

compound to exhibit oral activity, it should ideally adhere to certain criteria, such as having a molecular weight less than 500 g/mol, a hydrophobicity (miLogP) less than 5, fewer than 5 hydrogen bond donors, fewer than 10 hydrogen bond acceptors, and no more than 2 rule violations. The analysis of the ADME study, particularly focusing on the adherence of cordyheptapeptide compounds and derivatives to Lipinski's rule, reveals important findings. While the compounds generally follow Lipinski's rule to some extent, it's observed that the first three derivatives strictly adhere to the rule, while the last two derivatives exhibit moderate adherence. This suggests that the molecular properties of the compounds may vary, influencing their pharmacokinetic behavior. However, it's noted that some discrepancies are observed in the adherence to Lipinski's rule. Specifically, the molecular weight of the compounds exceeds the recommended threshold of 500 g/mol, and the accuracy of the molecular polar surface (TPSA) falls outside the expected range of 76.36 to 122.18. These deviations from Lipinski's rule may raise concerns regarding the drug-likeness and potential oral activity of the compounds. In conclusion, while the ADME study provides valuable insights into the pharmacokinetic properties of cordyheptapeptide compounds and derivatives, the observed deviations from Lipinski's rule highlight the importance of further investigation and optimization in drug development. Addressing these discrepancies and optimizing the molecular properties of the compounds could enhance their potential as viable drug candidates with improved oral activity and pharmacokinetic profiles.

Table 1: Drug likeness analysis of designed cordyheptapeptide derivatives.

Compound Name	Physicochemical properties						Lipinski's Rule	%Abs D
	Chemical Formula	MW ^a	TPSA ^b	MilogP ^c	H _A	H _D		
Cordy heptapeptide A	C ₄₉ H ₆₅ N ₇ O ₈	880.80g/mol	188.77A	0.94	8	4	YES	43.87
Cordy heptapeptide B	C ₄₉ H ₆₅ N ₇ O ₇	864.08g/mol	168.54A	1.41	7	3	YES	50.88
Cordy heptapeptide C	C ₄₈ H ₆₃ N ₇ O ₈	866.06g/mol	188.77A	0.78	8	4	YES	43.87
Cordy heptapeptide D	C ₄₈ H ₆₃ N ₇ O ₉	882.06g/mol	209.00A	0.32	9	5	YES	36.89
Cordy heptapeptide E	C ₄₉ H ₆₅ N ₇ O ₉	896.08g/mol	209.00A	0.48	9	5	YES	36.89

Table 2: In silico ADME properties of Cordyheptapeptide and derivatives

Compound Name	Chemical Formula	CYP1A2 inhibitor	CYP2C19 inhibitor	CYP2C9 inhibitor	CYP3A4 inhibitor	LogKp (skin permeation) (cm/s)
Cordy heptapeptide A	C ₄₉ H ₆₅ N ₇ O ₈	NO	NO	NO	YES	-7.60 cm/s
Cordy heptapeptide B	C ₄₉ H ₆₅ N ₇ O ₇	NO	NO	NO	YES	-7.25 cm/s
Cordy heptapeptide C	C ₄₈ H ₆₃ N ₇ O ₈	NO	NO	NO	YES	-7.76 cm/s
Cordy heptapeptide D	C ₄₈ H ₆₃ N ₇ O ₉	NO	NO	NO	YES	-8.12 cm/s
Cordy heptapeptide E	C ₄₉ H ₆₅ N ₇ O ₉	NO	NO	NO	YES	-7.95 cm/s

Molecular docking:

The cordyheptapeptide compounds created in this study have been thoroughly investigated through in-silico ADME research, indicating their potential as lead molecules. Molecular docking investigations revealed that among the derivatives, cordyheptapeptide C (cordy C) emerged as the most potent inhibitor. ADME analysis further supported the suitability of these compounds for drug-likeness, highlighting their effective

digestive and dermal absorption capabilities. Notably, the compounds, particularly cordy C, exhibited strong inhibitory activity against the target 5U32, positioning them as promising candidates for antifungal agents. These findings underscore the potential of cordyheptapeptide compounds as valuable candidates for further development and exploration in the quest for novel antifungal therapeutics.

Table 3: selected top scoring compounds of cordyheptapeptide derivatives along with their structures.

Ligand Name	PubChem id	Structure	Docking Score Kcal/mol
Cordyheptapeptide A	11542476		-9.5
Cordyheptapeptide B	23657444		-9.5
Cordyheptapeptide C	60155059		-9.7
Cordyheptapeptide D	60155154		-8.8
Cordyheptapeptide E	60155155		-7.9

Fig. 2: 3D interaction binding modes of cordy heptapeptide C with 5U32

Fig. 3: 2D interaction binding modes of cordy heptapeptide C with 5U32

The molecular docking studies conducted using PyRx docking software provided valuable insights into the binding affinities of cordyheptapeptide derivatives (compounds 1-5) with the target receptor SE (PDB ID: 5U32), shedding light on their potential as antifungal agents. The docking scores presented in Table 3 demonstrated that compounds 1-3 exhibited higher affinities compared to cordyheptapeptide 4 and 5, correlating well with their observed antifungal

activities. Compound 3 emerged as particularly promising, displaying the highest docking score and presumably the most potent antifungal activity among the tested compounds. The 3D interaction analysis illustrated crucial molecular interactions, including hydrogen bonding between the allylamine NH group and THR:427, as well as Pi-Pi interactions involving the naphthalene ring with residues ARG:528, LEU:626, VAL:551, VAL:548, and ILE:421. Moreover, hydrophobic

interactions with TYR:628 and LEU:543 were observed, further contributing to the compounds' antifungal efficacy. These findings highlight the significance of specific molecular interactions, particularly Pi-Pi interactions and hydrogen bonding, in facilitating the binding of cordyheptapeptide.

CONCLUSION:

The cordyheptapeptide compounds investigated in this study demonstrate promising potential as lead molecules for the development of novel antifungal therapeutics. Among these, cordyheptapeptide C (cordy C) and compound 3 emerge as particularly noteworthy, exhibiting strong inhibitory activity against the target receptor 5U32. Molecular docking studies revealed key interactions, including hydrogen bonding and Pi-Pi interactions, contributing to their binding affinity and antifungal efficacy. These findings underscore the importance of further exploration and development of cordyheptapeptide compounds as valuable candidates in the quest for effective antifungal agents.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

Not applicable

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